

The imperative to archive. On International Tracing Service (Arolsen Archives) mission and its impact on collective European memory of the Holocaust – report from research at the Wiener Holocaust Library in London¹

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Abstract

The presented report from research at the Wiener Holocaust Library in London focuses on International Tracing Service (from 2019 operating under the name The Arolsen Archives – International Center on Nazi Persecution), world's biggest archive on Holocaust victims and survivors, which mission and impact are addressed in the context of the collective European memory of the Holocaust.

Key words: International Tracing Service, Arolsen Archives, archive, memory, Holocaust

Anna Kuchta, dr; naukowczyni w Katedrze Porównawczych Studiów Cywilizacji Uniwersytetu Jagiellońskiego w Krakowie; doktorka nauk humanistycznych w dyscyplinie nauki o kulturze i religii (2019); z jednej strony pasjonuje się Japonią – literaturą, kulturą popularną (w tej perspektywie bada powieść *Genji Monogatari*), przemianami społecznymi, z drugiej – kondycją kultury współczesnej, zagadnieniami postpamięci i tożsamości kulturowej. Stypendystka SYLFF (The Ryoichi Sasakawa Young Leaders Fellowship Fund) w roku 2016 oraz The Holocaust Research Institute (Royal Holloway, University of London) w roku 2022

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Facta Ficta.

Journal of Theory, Narrative & Media

¹ This research was funded in whole by National Science Centre, Poland, project no. 2023/07/X/HS3/00342.

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18140737

International Tracing Service (hereafter: ITS), known today (since 2019) as Arolsen Archives¹, is an institution that was born out of necessity – from the unparalleled number of missing people, abundance of refugees from various countries, plethora of lost children, broken families and broken connections after the Second World War. As described by Dan Stone, it “emerged out of tracing efforts already in train at the end of the war, being run by numerous organizations, including Jewish and Catholic charities, the Quakers, and the Red Cross” (Stone 2024: 7) and soon became the biggest initiative focused on finding the missing after the war. During my research at the Wiener Holocaust Library in London², United Kingdom’s sole point of access to the ITS archive, I traced (pun intended) whether and how such an institution impacted the process of shaping the memory of the Holocaust in the postwar Europe.

The awareness of “a humanitarian crisis on a historically unprecedented scale” (Borggräfe, Höschler & Panek 2019: 9) and the need to locate the missing people and to document their fate have been already recognized and converted into concrete actions during the Second World War as some of the ITS precursor organizations (including, for example American Jewish Joint Distribution Committee or British Red Cross) started their important work even before 1945. But it was the year 1948 when ITS officially came into existence under such name and with the main objective to focus on finding individuals. This central idea of the mission is not only stated in the documents on ITS establishment and history (see Arolsen Archives, DocID: 82492866; Arolsen Archives, DocID: 82503493; Arolsen Archives, DocID: 82493195),

¹ Despite the 2019 name change, this essay mostly refers to the institution as International Tracing Service (ITS) as it is primary focused on the period of time when that name was officially in use.

² My visit to The Wiener Holocaust Library in London was a part of research project “The Role of International Tracing Service (ITS) in Shaping Collective Memory of the Holocaust”, no. 2023/07/X/HS3/00342, funded by National Science Centre, Poland and took place in June 2024. I hereby The Wiener Holocaust library staff for warm welcome and research guidance during my visit.

but also clearly visible in the structure of the archive itself, with the Central Name Index (containing over 50 million cards regarding about 17 500 million people) as its core.

What is particularly important when analyzing the history of ITS, is that the conceptualization of the institution as well as the need to document war fates of individuals were inherently an international effort and need. The concept that both the scale and the response to the Holocaust and the Second World War should be seen and addressed in pan-European³ context was present from the very beginning, which should be highlighted as significant when considering the formation of the collective memory of the Holocaust. International cooperation for a common purpose of Holocaust reckoning and remembrance was fitting perfectly into after war idea of European integration (Stone 2014: X) on the basis on shared traumatic experience – something that also served as a foundational story of the European Union (Assmann A. 2014; Kucia 2016). And despite a few setbacks (the biggest being probably the conflict between Western and Eastern Europe after 1945 and the cold war preventing the flow of information and exchange of documents), this international scope of ITS is still present today. Currently, the institution is being overseen by The International Commission formed by representatives from eleven countries (Belgium, France, Federal Republic of Germany, Greece, Israel, Italy, Luxembourg, The Netherlands, Poland, United Kingdom, United States of America).

Thanks to ITS amazing effort to preserve evidence, collect the documents and – subsequently – to use them in order to solve cases of unknown victims and missing survivors, the archive has already answered pressing questions of numerous people and their work in this matter is by no means over⁴. But there is more in the history of ITS than responding to personal and legal inquires that should be viewed in the sphere of collective memory construction processes. Regardless of the initial purpose of the institution and the “humanitarian mission” (Borggräfe, Höschler & Panek 2019: 17) at its core, it is undeniable that ITS had impact on the memory of the Holocaust in Europe on more than individual (or family-related) level.

In the twentieth century there was no united policy on whether the ITS should restrict (or even isolate) the content of its archives (with strictly limited access, only allowing personal or legal inquires) or have them vastly accessible to people not directly connected to the missing or Holocaust and

³ Or even: global, with the obvious involvement of the United States of America or Israel. While the importance of global approach is certainly important, for the purpose of this essay European perspective will be highlighted.

⁴ According to the Arolsen Archives’ website each year the archive receives “inquiries about more than 20,000 people; about two thirds of these inquiries come from relatives” (Arolsen-archives.org 2024a).

Second World War victims (e.g. Holocaust researchers, historians or educators). Discussions and disputes surrounding this dilemma can be seen as a reflection of Holocaust memory politics forming in Europe after the war. What is sometimes forgotten in the complex history of International Tracing Service is that in the 1960s there were numerous academic and memorial projects carried at the archive, including those handled by outside teams. Such “phase of openness”, as referred to by Henning Borggräfe, Christian Höschler and Isabel Panek (18), however, ended rather abruptly⁵ in the 1980s, starting the decades of closure, which are often brought up when addressing limited impact the ITS could have had on collective memory of the Shoah. How, one may ask, could such an isolated collection impact the collective memory of the Holocaust? The answer is somehow paradoxical – the abrupt closure of the ITS archives in the 1980s resulted in vivid public response, which itself can be viewed as important activity in terms of memory cultures formulation.

Firstly, there was a debate in West Germany in regard to coming to terms with the past, which corresponds well with the growing inclusion of Holocaust memory into common European awareness (Judt 2010; Mach 2016), prompted by crucial events of 1960s and 1970s (including the 1961 trial of Adolf Eichmann, the 1972 Summer Olympics in Munich and the premiere of NBC miniseries *Holocaust* in 1978). The public demand – and outrage⁶ – to access the archive can be therefore recognized as an important step in understanding the Holocaust as a part of shared past and also a signal that the memory of the Shoah was considered “common” – people with no personal connection insisted on opening the archive as its content was seen as vital for common, not simply individual memory. Additionally there was a constant pressure from scholars and representatives of various educational and memorial agencies (the work of Paul Shapiro from the United States Holocaust Memorial Museum is considered especially impactful; Borggräfe, Höschler & Panek 2019: 19) to open the archive. Research, educational and commemoration needs were perpetually raised by various stakeholders until ITS finally reopening in 2007⁷. This, once again, can be viewed as a reflection of growing need to understand the history as well as treating the Holocaust remembrance as a common responsibility. Those voices corresponded with

⁵ As pointed by Borggräfe, Höschler & Panek (17) the changes were often simply a result of different directors’ approaches towards ITS governance, with no clear long-term policy for the institution established.

⁶ The protests went as far as accusing the ITS of intentionally hiding – and thus helping – the Nazi perpetrators (Borggräfe, Höschler & Panek 2019: 18) – even though it was the concern regarding data security and privacy that was, most likely, the primary cause of isolation (Stone 2024: 398).

⁷ A small part of the archive was technically made available earlier (in 1996), but obtaining the documents was not easily accessible (Borggräfe, Höschler & Panek 2019: 18).

needs of the second (and third) generation entering the discourse of the Holocaust and searching for their roots.

Therefore, a claim can be formed that even during the prolonged period of isolation, ITS had an impact on memory culture in Europe. Moreover – as described in detail by Stone in his recent (and monumental!) work on International Tracing Service – it was the ITS archives which allowed both persons looking for their families as well as historians to look at individual life stories through a different lence and with a wider perspective (Stone 2024: 398). The abundance of data in ITS archives – much of which is still waiting to be properly researched – provides a unique resource for Holocaust researchers and educators. Additionally, thanks to the ITS constant self-awareness and including documents related to the history of the archive itself, it can also be used to reflect on European memory culture as well. Nowadays, the approach of the archive follows the principle of long-awaited openness, which started in 2007, as the website clearly states that “guests are very welcome to visit the Arolsen Archives in person. The world’s most comprehensive archive on the victims of National Socialism is open to al.” (Arolsen-archives.org 2024b) and provides easily understandable guidance in regard to accessing the archives. Ideas of modernization, accessibility and digitalization are visibly present in current goals of the archive and the change in how the institution wants to be viewed by the public is reflected in new name – Arolsen Archives: International Center on Nazi Persecution – which also highlights the ever-present and aforementioned international focus. One may anticipate that with recently-applied “open doors” policy, the archive will serve as source of multidimensional research projects and will reclaim its place in the discourse on Holocaust memory in Europe.

Źródła cytowań

- AROLSEN ARCHIVES, DE ITS 6 – Records of the ITS and its predecessors, 6.1.1 Documents on the administrative history and the activities of the ITS, 1945 – 1951, DocID: 82492866.
- AROLSEN ARCHIVES, DE ITS 6 – Records of the ITS and its predecessors, 8323001 – Documents on the administrative history and the activities of the ITS, 1945 – 1951, DocID: 82493195.
- AROLSEN ARCHIVES, DE ITS 6 – Records of the ITS and its predecessors, 8323039 – International Refugee Organization, General Council, Sessions I – V, 1948 – 1950, DocID: 82503493.
- AROLSEN-ARCHIVES.ORG, (2024a). 'Information for relatives of victims of Nazi persecution', online: <https://arolsen-archives.org/en/search-explore/inquiries/information-for-relatives/> [accessed: 02.07.2024].
- AROLSEN-ARCHIVES.ORG, (2024b). 'Visit us', online: <https://arolsen-archives.org/en/visit-us/> [accessed: 02.07.2024].
- ASSMANN, ALEIDA, (2014), 'Transnational Memories', in *European Review*: 22 (4), p. 546-556.
- BORGGRÄFE, HENNING, CHRISTIAN HÖSCHLER, ISABEL PANEK, (2019), 'A Paper Monument: Introduction', in Henning Borggräfe, Christian Höschler and Isabel Panek on behalf of the Arolsen Archives (ed.), *A Paper Monument: The History of the Arolsen Archives. Catalogue of the permanent exhibition*, Bad Arolsen: Oeding print, p. 8-19.
- JUDT, TONY, (2010), *Postwar: a history of Europe since 1945*, London: Vintage Books.
- KUCIA, MAREK, (2016), 'The Europeanization of Holocaust Memory and Eastern Europe', in *East European Politics and Societies*, 30 (1), p. 97-119.
- MACH, ANNA, (2016), *Świadkowie świadectw. Postpamięć Zagłady w polskiej literaturze najnowszej*, Warszawa–Toruń: Fundacja na Rzecz Nauki Polskiej.
- STONE, DAN, (2023), *Fate Unknown. Tracing the Missing after World War II and the Holocaust*, Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- STONE, DAN, (2014), *Goodbye to all that?: a history of Europe since 1945*, Oxford: Oxford University Press.